

percent of farmers' fields carried HW during kharif, 2) to determine the constraints on the transfer of technology and the constraints the farmers face in efficient pest management, and 3) to study how the gap between the farmers' yield and that achieved at rice experimental stations can be minimized. The farmers are being trained and encouraged to adopt improved packages of practices; to integrate different methods of pest management such as nursery treatment, use of more or less specific pesticides (preferably granular formulations when the insect population is at the economic threshold), weed control, land tillering after harvest, close cutting of the crop, planting of resistant varieties, use of light traps for monitoring; and surveillance, crop rotation, and other relevant practices.

The Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests aims at an interdisciplinary attack on other farmers' problems as well as pest management.

Some insecticide schedules tested against the paddy ear-cutting caterpillar in rice

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Some insecticide schedules were tested in 4- x 3-m plots of Saket-4, a rice that matures in about 110 days, during the July–October 1975 season at the Regional Agricultural Testing and Demonstration Centre, Varanasi, India. Combinations of paddy-water application of carbofuran, mephospolan, phorate, and disulfoton granules, and foliar sprays of fenitrothion and Ambithion were tested. Larval counts were taken at 76 days after transplanting (DT) by checking 20 hills diagonally across each plot.

The poorest control (1.8 larvae/hill) was attained with one application of 1.2 kg a.i. disulfoton/ha at 25 DT. None of the granules or sprays provided adequate control when applied alone. Results indicated that granules should be applied in combination with foliar sprays up to 65 DT to control ear-cutting caterpillar on early maturing varieties.

Incidence of rice gall midge and its parasites in Karnataka, India

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The rice gall midge is endemic in coastal Karnataka State. During the last 3 years, its presence has also been noted in the interior. Incidence has been severe in the summer crop. In summer 1975, 49 slender-grain cultivars were planted in three replications. The growing season varied from 92 to 120 days. The percentage of hills showing galls varied from 16.6 to 70.3. The number of galls per square meter varied from 9.5 in IET 3368 to 65.5 in IET 3201. All cultivars were susceptible to attack.

From the gall midge affected plants collected in the field, the following parasites emerged in the laboratory:

Platygastridae – *Platygastr* sp.
Eupelmidae – *Neanastatus grallarius* (Masi)

Eulophidae – *Tetrastichus* sp.

Braconidae – ? *Gyrocampa* sp.

Ichneumonidae – *Gelis areator* (Panzer)

Ceratopogonidae – Unidentified

Of the six, *Platygastr* sp. and *Neanastatus* sp. parasitized more than 50% of the larvae.

Occurrence of the American rice water weevil in Japan

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In May 1976, the rice water weevil *Lissorprus oryzophilus* Kuschel was found in two regions of Aichi prefecture. The reports were the first of the pest in Japan. Specimens were sent to Australia and identified by Dr. G. Kuschel.

In the region of Tokoname, the weevils occurred in paddy fields of 600 ha. Over 10 grubs per hill were found on rice roots in June; rice plants were severely injured. In the region of Koda cho, about 30 m away from Tokoname, about 130 ha were damaged by the weevil. It is supposed that the

insect immigrated with hay imported from America 1 or 2 years earlier. Since the male adults have never been found, the insects are considered a parthenogenetic strain.

Brown planthopper attack in East Godavari, A.P., India

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Of about 1 million ha of rabi 1976 paddy that was grown in nine blocks in East Godavari District, India, about 3,250 ha was severely infested by brown planthoppers (BHP) and an estimated 200 ha suffered hopperburn. Many other fields harbored 100 to 1,000 BHP per clump by early April. Yield loss appeared widespread. RP 4-14 and Jaya were extensively grown among high yielding varieties.

Some 8- to 16-ha farms that received only one application of granular carbofuran, 40 to 50 days after planting, were practically free of BHP, while much of the nearby area received repeated insecticidal sprays at intervals of 7 to 10 days from 10 to 15 days after planting and suffered severe infestations. A survey in early April revealed hectic dusting or spraying in affected fields at 3- to 4-day intervals. Spiders, beetles, and hymenopterous parasites were absent from such fields. Indiscriminate, repeated spraying beginning with the early crop stage may have been responsible for the unprecedented outbreak. Dense plantings (70 to 90 clumps/sq m), while affording a favorable microclimate for BHP buildup, rendered sprays ineffective. An integrated strategy for combating the menace was tested in kharif 1976. BHP-resistant, high yielding cultures like CR57-MR.1523 were grown without plant protection, or susceptible varieties were grown and the following treatments were applied: dipping seedling roots for 12 hours in 0.02% chlorpyrifos before transplanting, transplanting not more than 40 to 50 hills/sq m, and applying granular insecticides when necessary on the basis of economic thresholds.